

Research Paper

Formulation And Evaluation of Antioxidant Rich Semisolid Poly Herbal Hair Mask for Dandruff

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ABSTRACT

Objectives: To formulate and evaluate poly herbal hair mask **Materials And Methods:** The hair mask was made using a variety of herbal substance such as bael fruit, bael leaves, fenugreek, tulsi, neem leaves, curry leaves, coconut oil, castor oil, hibiscus flower, reetha, amla powder, vitamin E, aloe vera gel, flax seed gel and sodium benzoate, Before combining the components with oils gels and preservatives they must first be obtained, cleaned, dried, powdered and weighed. The herbal hair mask formulation was evaluated based on several criteria including pH, viscosity and other physico chemical parameters, stability test, organoleptic evaluation, phytochemical evaluation and microbial assay, **RESULTS:** The study aimed to create and evaluate a poly herbal hair mask using various herbal substances. The mask was tested for its organoleptic properties, pH, viscosity, and stability. Results showed that F2 was the best formulation, with no chemical presence and no side effects on the scalp. The mask's color, texture, and odor were all satisfactory. The mask was also found to be easily washable and had good spreadability and homogeneity. The microbial assay showed good zone of inhibition for both F1 and F2. **Conclusion:** The hair mask that was made to contain no chemicals. It contained all natural composition means that it has no side effect on the scalp.

INTRODUCTION

Healthy hair builds confidence in people by improving appearance among themselves. The human skin and hair have a vital role in communication. Length, color, and style of a person's hair greatly influence how they perceive themselves physically. To keep hair healthy,

further care must be taken.^[1] A frequent non-contagious hair condition that almost affects everyone, regardless of age is dandruff. Pityriasis simplex capitis is the shedding of dead scalp skin in medical term. Which appears to be greasy or dry, as greasy flakes appears pale yellowish with undesirable odour, dry dandruff is silvery and

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white in appearance.^[2] Itching and unpleasant dandruff is mostly caused by keratinocytes, which are also responsible for the expression of immune responses during dandruff growth and development.^[3] A frequent noncontagious hair condition that age is dandruff.^[4] Although dandruff is mostly invisible, there are a number of contributing reasons such as greasy scalp in adequate fungal infections are caused by poor personal hygiene and a weak dirty the scalp, which can make it worse.^[5] This disorder results in the production of scalp flakes, which itch the skin. Different individuals have diverse hair kinds like normal, greasy and dry hair.^[6] The market is filled with numerous herbal formulations. Plants and essential oils are examples of herbal ingredients. Herb-based cosmetics have seen tremendous rise in the natural products market in the last few days.^[7]

Ideal properties of poly herbal hair mask

1. Moisturizing ; Hydrates and nourishes the hair and scalp.^[8]
2. Nourishing: Offers vital antioxidants, vitamins, and minerals for healthy hair growth.^[9]

3. Protective: Prevents heat style, chemical processing, and environmental harm to hair.^[9]
4. pH balanced: Prevents dryness and irritation by preserving the scalp's natural pH.^[10]

Advantages of semisolid hair mask over liquid herbal formulations

1. Semi Solid poly herbal hair masks are more stable than liquid and have longer shelf lives.^[11]
2. These are easy to pack, handle, ship and transport.^[12]
3. Patients are able to self administer semi solid herbal hair mask more easily when compared to liquid preparations.^[13]
4. Good penetration and contact time between hair mask and scalp.^[14]

Disadvantages

1. Semi solid poly herbal hair mask causes product builds up.^[15]
2. Can leave small gritty particles on the hair.^[16]

Mechanism of Dandruff formation:

Plant Profile

Sl. No	Common Name	Synonyms	Biological Source (Bs) & Family(F)	Active Constituents	Uses

1.	Bael fruit & Bael leaves	Stone apple	BS- It is derived from the fruit of the <i>Aegle marmelos tree</i> F- <i>Rutaceae</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Alkaloids Glycosides Flavanoids 	Used to promote hair growth and reduce dandruff.
2.	Flax seed gel	Linseed	BS- It is derived from the seeds of the <i>Linum usitatissimum</i> plant F- <i>Linaceae</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Omega-3 fatty acids Protein Mucilage 	Used to nourish and condition hair.
3.	Fenugreek	Greek hay	BS- derived from the seeds of the <i>Trigonella foenum- graecum</i> plant F- <i>Fabaceae</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Saponins Alkaloids Flavanoids Fibers Protein Vitamins 	Used to promote hair growth, reduce dandruff and improve scalp health .
4.	Tulsi	Holy basil	BS- derived from the leaves of the <i>Ocimum sanctum</i> plant F- <i>Lamiaceae</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Volatile oils Alkaloids Glycosides Flavonoids 	It has hair growth promoting and dandruff reducing property
5.	Aloe vera gel	Aloe latex	BS- It is derived from the leaves of the <i>Aloe barbadensis</i> plant F- <i>Asphodelaceae</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Aloin Aloe-emodin Vitamins A,C & E 	Used to promote hair growth, dandruff and sooth scalp irritations.
6.	Curry leaves	Sweet neem	BS- derived from the leaves of the <i>Murraya koenigii</i> tree F- <i>Rutaceae</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Volatile oil Alkaloids Flavanoids Tannins Vitamins 	Used to promote hair growth and reduce dandruff.
7.	Hibiscus flower	Roselle sorrel	BS- It is derived from the <i>Hibiscus sabdariffa</i> plant F- <i>Malvaceae</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Organic acids Flavonoids Vitamins Anthocyanin Poly-saccharides 	Used to promote hair growth and reduce dandruff.
8.	Amla	Emblica officinalis	BS- It is derived from fruit of the <i>Emblica officinalis</i> F- <i>Phyllanthaceae</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Ascorbic acid Tannins Flavonoids Alkaloids 	Used to promote hair growth, reduce dandruff and improve scalp health.
9.	Reeta	Soapnut reetha	BS- derived from the fruit of the <i>Sapindus mukorossi</i> tree F- <i>Sapindaceae</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Saponin Flavonoids Tannins Alkaloids 	Used as a natural shampoo and hair cleanser.

10.	Neem leaves	Indian lilac	BS- It is derived from the Azadirachtaindica tree F- Meliaceae	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Azadirachtin • Nimbin • Nimbidin • Quercetin • Salannin 	It has dandruff reducing, lice killing and hair growth promoting properties.
11.	Coconut oil(virgin)	Copra oil	BS- <i>Cocous nucifera</i> F- <i>Arcaceae</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Medium chain triglycerides • Fatty acid • Antimicrobial 	Moisturizes and nourishes the hair Repair and damage
12.	Castor oil	Ricinus oil	BS- <i>Ricinus communis</i> F- <i>Euphorbiaceae</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Fatty acid • Alkaloids 	Laxatives & Purgatives
13.	Vitamin-E	Tocopherol	BS-Vegetable oil F- <i>Tocotrieno</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Tocopherols (α, β, γ, δ) • Tocotrienols (α, β, γ, δ) 	Antioxidant & Anti-ageing properties

Excipient Profile

Sl No	Common Name	Synonyms	Biological Source (Bs) & Family(F)	Active Constituents	Uses
1.	Sodium benzoate	Benzoic acid sodium salt	BS-Derived from benzoic acid	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Sodium benzoate 	Antifungal & Antibacterial

MATERIALS AND METHODOLOGY:

Preparation of aloe vera gels :

The Aloevera (*Aloebarbadensis*) plant's thick, succulent leaves were acquired from a herbal garden. Aloevera leaves were collected, cleaned with water and a moderate chlorine solution, and then the mucilaginous jelly extracted from the plant's centre was used to make Aloevera extract.^[17]

Preparation of flax seed gels:

In a saucepan about 2 cups of water was made to boil, about 4 table spoon of flax seed were added to the boiling water. Reduce the heat to simmer and cook for 5-7 minutes, or until the mixture thickens and flaxseeds absorbed most of the water. The mixture was Strained through a cotton cloth or a fine mesh strainer into a bowl, pressing on the solids to extract as much as

possible discard the solids. Let the gel cool to room temperature.^[18]

Formulations:

Method:

The herbal ingredients were collected from domestic area and medicinal plant garden of our college and shade dried leaves were grinded separately to form a powder. Each herbal powder was grounded using mortar and pestle and thoroughly triturated, and sieved using sieve number 80 to get a fine powder before being added to the formulation. Accurately weighed amount of oil(virgin), castor oil and vitamin E were added and mixture is triturated well. Extracted gels of aloevera and flax seed gel were added and triturated well.¹⁹ Sodium benzoate was added and triturated well until the semisolid form is obtained.^[20]

Formulation Table

Sl.no	Ingredients	F1	F2	F3
1.	Bael fruit/leaves	(5+5)	(4+6)	(6+6)
2.	Flaxseedgel	20	25	15
3.	Fenugreek seed	5	5	7
4.	Tulsi	5.5	5.5	6.5
5.	Aleo vera gel	30	25	20
6.	Neem leaves	6	6	6.5

7.	Coconut oil (virgin)	3	3	6
8.	Castor oil	2	2	4
9.	Vitamin E	2	2	4
10.	Curry leaves	5.5	5.5	5.5
11.	Hibiscus flower	2	2	4
12.	Amla	4	4	5
13.	Reetha	3	3	3
14.	Sodium benzoate	2	2	2
15.	Water	qs	Qs	qs

Evaluation:

Organoleptic evaluation : Formulations was observed for the presence of color, odour, texture and appearance. ^[21]

Physico –Chemical Evaluation:

pH: The pH of the formulations was measured at a fixed temperature using a calibrated digital pH meter. ^[22]

Spreadability:

A glass sliding gadget and wooden block were used to assess the hair mask's spreadability. The block's bottom was covered with a precise 5 gm of hair mask, and then the upper slide was adjusted. After that, the amount of time needed for the upper slide to detach 5 cm from the assembly was noted. Spreadability was calculated using the formula. ^[23]

$$S = \frac{m \times l}{t}$$

S is the spreadability, m is the weight attached to the upper slide, l is the distance travelled by the upper slide, and t is the time it takes to separate the slides. ^[24]

Homogeneity:

After being spread out on a glass slide for appearance, the prepared gels were visually inspected for homogeneity and scrutinized for the presence of lumps, flocculates, or aggregates. ^[25]

Viscosity:

Viscosity was measured using a Brookfield viscometer. In addition a large mouth jar was filled with an adequate amount of gel; the gel's height in the jar should have allowed the spindle to dip. The spindle was set to run at 2.5 RPM. The formulation viscosities were observed. ^[26]

Loss On Drying:

Measure approximately 1.5 grams of the formulation in a petri dish. After allowing the desiccators to cool and recording the weight, place it in oven temperature was set at 100°C or 105° until there is a maximum 0.5 gram difference between two successive weights.

Typically, any weight reduction is due to the loss of moisture. ^[27]

Patch Test:

On the hands a little of the formulated mixture is applied and recorded for any itching and irritation. ^[28]

Stability Test:

The formulation was kept under various humidity and temperature conditions (ranging from 35° to 40°), and changes in its physical properties were observed. ^[29]

Phytochemical Screening: -

Numerous experiments were conducted to establish the type of phytoconstituents that were present in the products and type of adverse reactions produced within the body. Every plant has unique phytochemical features that give a variety of useful effects. ^[30]

a) Detection of carbohydrate-**I. Molisch's Test-**

To 2-3 ml of aqueous extract, add a few drops of alpha-naphthol solution in alcohol. Shake, then add conc-H₂SO₄ from the sides of the test tube. At the intersection of the two liquids, a violet ring formed. ^[31]

II. Fehling's Test-

Fehling's Test: Heat the combination of Fehling A and Fehling B solutions for one minute. Introduce the test solution in a matching quantity. Place it in a pot of boiling water and continue heating for 5 to 10 minutes. Brick red followed by initial yellow streaks will appear. ^[32]

b) Detection of alkaloids

I. Hagers Test-

Hager's reagent produces a yellow precipitate in 2-3 ml of the filtrate. [33]

II. Mayer's Test-

Add about a few drops of Mayer's reagent to 2-3 ml of the filtrate results in the formation of a creamy precipitate. [34]

c) Detection of Volatile Oil-

When volatile oils are present, the hair mask made from 2 to 4 grams of Sudan III alcoholic solution will turn red. [35]

d) Detection of Protein-

Biuret Test - Add 4% NaOH to 3 ml of the test solution, followed by a few drops of 1% CuSO₄ solution. A violet or pink color will be observed. [36]

e) Foam Test-

Mix the dry powder or extract with water. A stable foam that lasts for a long time was noted. [37]

Microbial Assay:

Procedure to Detect Minimum Inhibitory Concentration:

In vitro detection of minimum inhibitory concentration were examined for given sample. The agar diffusion method was used to examine minimum inhibitory concentration of samples against bacteria. The samples were used for the determination of zone of inhibition or sensitivity, against test pathogen Staphylococcus aureus bacterial strain. The minimum inhibitory

concentration for bacteria was performed on nutrient agar medium. The nutrient agar was prepared as per the composition mentioned below , autoclaved for 121⁰ C for 15 LBS and cooled and poured on sterilized petri plates and allowed for solidification. After solidification test pathogen was inoculated on to the medium, later the wells were created and sample was introduced. For a whole day, the plates were incubated at 35⁰C. Growth inhibition activity was monitored on the incubated plates. [38]

Table 3.0

Nutrient Agar	
Composition	Quantity (%)
Peptone	0.5%
Yeast extract	0.3%
Sodium chloride	0.5%
Agar	1.5%
pH	6.8±0.2

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

Organoleptic Evaluation:

Formulated poly Herbal hair mask was examined for various organoleptic parameter as indicated in Table 3.1 The colour of the formulation was olive green , odor was pleasant , texture was semi solid and appearance was smooth. [39]

Table 3.1: Organoleptic Evaluation:

Sl No	Parameters	F1	F2	F3
1.	Colour	Olive green	Olive green	Olive green
2.	Oduor	Pleasant	Pleasant	Pleasant
3.	Texture	Semi solid	Semi solid	Semi solid
4.	Appearance	Smooth	Smooth	Smooth

Physicochemical Evaluation:

Table 3.2 displays the physicochemical parameters that were assessed for the herbal hair mask. The pH of formulation was found to be 5.9 – 6.0, washability was easily washable, spreadability was good, homogeneity

was homogenous, patch test was no irritation and cleansing was good. [40]

Table 3.2: Physico-Chemical Evaluation

Sl No	Parameters	F1	F2	F3	Figueres
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1.	pH	6	5.9	5.9	
2.	Washability	Easily washable	Easily washable	Easily washable	
3.	Spreadability	Good	Best	Good	
4.	Homogeneity	Homogenous	Homogenous	Homogenous	
5.	Patch test	No irritation	No irritation	No irritation	

Loss On Drying:

Herbal hair mask was evaluated for physicochemical parameter of moisture loss on drying within the limit.^[41]

Formulations	Loss On Drying	Figures
F1.	104%	
F2.	108%	
F3.	104%	

F1 (Spindle number -64)

SL NO	RPM	Viscosity
1.	2.5	3,960 Cp
2.	10	13,800 cP
3.	25	10,220 cP
4.	50	5,292 cP

F2 (Spindle number-64)

SL NO	RPM	Viscosity
1.	2.5	66,000 cP
2.	10	28,800 cP
3.	25	16,800 cP
4.	50	9,432 cP

Viscosity:

Stability Studies:

Table 3.3: Stability Test

SI No	Parameters	Results	Figures
1.	Alteration in colour	No change	
2.	Alteration in odour	No change	
3.	Alteration in texture	No change	
4.	Alteration in appearance	No change	

Phytochemical Screening:

Phytochemical screening study was carried out for formulation to test for the presence of phytochemical and the result are given below in the table

Table 3.4: Phytochemical Screening

SlNo	Test	F1	F2	F3	Figures
1.	Detection of carbohydrate-	Positive	Positive	Positive	
	I. Molisch's Test-				
	II. Fehling's Test-	Positive	Positive	Positive	
2.	Detection of alkaloids-	Positive	Positive	Positive	
	I. Mayer's test-				
3.	Detection of protein-	Negative	Negative	Negative	
4.	Foam test-	Positive	Positive	Positive	

Microbial Assay:

Poly Herbal hair mask was made to undergo evaluation studies for physicochemical parameter shown in table 3.5

Table 3.5: Microbial Assay

Detection of Minimum Inhibitory Concentration

Test Organism	Zone of Inhibition in Test Sample
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	Sample: F1			
	Concentration in mg			
	0.25	0.50	0.75	1.0
Staphylococcus aureus	0	0	0	2

Zone of Inhibition in Test Sample F1

Detection of Minimum Inhibitory Concentration

Test Organism	Zone of Inhibition in Test Sample							
	Sample: F2							
	Concentration in mg							
Staphylococcus aureus	0.25	0.50	0.75	1.0	1.25	1.50	1.75	2.0
	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	2

Zone of Inhibition in Test Sample F2

Summary

The study aimed to create a poly herbal hair mask using herbs with anti-bacterial, anti-inflammatory, and anti-oxidant properties. The mask was made using various plant parts, including bael fruit, bael leaves, fenugreek, tulsi, neem leaves, curry leaves, aloe vera, flax seed gel, coconut oil, castor oil, hibiscus flower, reetha, amla powder, vitamin E, and sodium benzoate. The mask was evaluated for pH, washability, spreadability, homogeneity, viscosity, patch test, loss on drying, stability test, organoleptic evaluation, phytochemical evaluation, and microbial assay. The results showed the mask was safer, more effective, and reasonably priced.

CONCLUSION

The study demonstrates the effectiveness of several plant-based medications in the development of hair care products. Since cosmetics made from herbs are well-known for their non-toxic properties, this poly herbal hair mask nourishes the scalp's skin while treating dandruff. Regular use of a formulated hair mask, which also adds shine to the hair, has proven to be a more effective therapy for dandruff, which is caused by excessive oily scalp and poor hygiene. Worldwide, the usage of herbal medicines is emerging. Since, in contrast to synthetic products, it is harmless and has fewer adverse effects. The evaluation study assures the anti-dandruff hair mask shelf life in the formulated product. An organoleptic study was performed in order to determine the color, texture, appearance, and odour. To determine the pH, washability, spreadability, homogeneity, patch test, cleansing, loss on drying, and viscosity. Physicochemical analysis was performed. Phytochemical evaluation was used to identify proteins, alkaloids, and carbohydrates. Stability test and microbial assay was evaluated. Microbial assay was carried out, it showed the significant outcomes. In

comparison of F1 and F2 formulations, good zone of inhibition was obtained in F2. The developed formulation has strong antibacterial properties against *Staphylococcus aureus*. This study shown that a formulated poly herbal anti-dandruff hair mask formulation is safe and suitable to use as a cosmeceutical.

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